

Recurrent Malignant Gliomas

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More Information

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Abstract

Materials and methods: We report a retrospective series of 120 patients treated for recurrent malignant gliomas with bevacizumab alone 2013-2018. There are 120 patients (pts) including 60 women and 80 Men with a sex ratio of 1.2. **Results:** There are 120 patients (pts) including 60 women and 80 Men with a sex ratio of 1.2. All patients had a surgery. the majority had a large or subtotal excision. 80 pts received Stupp protocole and 40 pts a radiotherapy alone. The reccurence was treated with Bevacizumab alone, 3 pts had a Complete Response, 40 Partial Response, 30 stable response and 45 pts a progression. We report a good tolerance, one pts had a proteinurie grade 3, one grade 1, one patient had a moderate high Blood Pressure, and the last one had a hematuria. **Conclusion:** Young age, good GE and quality of surgical excision are predictive factors for a good prognosis. Bevacizumab remains the recommended drug for recurrent glioblastomas with good tolerance.

Introduction

Glioblastoma (GBM) is the most common primary malignant tumor of the central nervous system (CNS), accounting for 46.6% of primary malignant brain tumors, 55.4% of gliomas, and 14.9% of all CNS tumors (including metastases) [1]. It predominantly affects adults and is more common in men than in women [2]. About 70% of cases involve individuals aged 45 to 70 years, with an average age at diagnosis of 58 years [3].

Materials and Methods

All patients underwent surgery. This retrospective series covers 120 patients treated for recurrent malignant gliomas with bevacizumab alone from 2013 to 2018. The cohort consists of 120 patients, including 60 women and 80 men, with a sex ratio of 1.2.

Figure 1: Sex Distribution

Table 2: Radiotherapy Distribution

	Radiothrapie
Radiothrapie alone	40
Stupp	80

Figure 2: Radiotherapy Distribution

Figure 3: Histological Distribution

Note: All patients underwent surgery

Table 2: Age Distribution

	Age (years)
20-30	20
30-40	25
40-50	35
50-60	30
60-70	10
Total	120

Figure 4: Age Distribution

The average age is 46.7 years (range 26-65).

Results (Treatment Response)

The combination of irinotecan and bevacizumab did not improve survival compared to bevacizumab alone and was poorly tolerated.

Combinations of other molecules with bevacizumab have not proven effective.

There are 120 patients (pts) including 60 women and 80 Men with a sex ratio of 1.2.

All patients had a surgery. the majority had a large or subtotal excision. 80 pts received Stupp protocole and 40 pts a radiotherapy alone. The recurrence was treated with Bevacizumab alone ,3 pts had a Complete Response, 40 Partial Response, 30 stable response and 45 pts a progression.

We report a good tolerance, one pts had a proteinurie grade 3, one grade 1, one patient had a moderate high Blood Pressure, and the last one had an hematuria.

Discussion

Issues: Treatments for Recurrent Gliomas

True progression must be distinguished from pseudo-progression, which occurs 1 to 12 weeks after initial treatment (40% of cases).

Treatment strategy for recurrence includes discussion in a multidisciplinary consultation meeting.

Consideration for neurosurgical reintervention?

Consideration for re-irradiation under stereotactic conditions?

Second-line Anti-angiogenic Treatments:

Carboplatin + etoposide: 20 to 30% response rate for high-grade recurrent gliomas, but no impact on Progression-Free Survival (PFS) or Overall Survival (OS). Reintroduction of temozolomide? After what interval? Standard or intensified regimen?

Bevacizumab: 50% response rate. PFS at 6 months = 40%.

The combination of irinotecan/bevacizumab does not offer a survival benefit compared to bevacizumab alone and appears to be poorly tolerated.

*The combinations of other molecules with bevacizumab have not been proven effective [4].

Figure 5: Recurrent Right Frontoparietal Grade III Oligoastrocytoma: 17/04/2013 before cycle 1 bevacizumab

Figure 6: Recurrent Right Frontoparietal Grade III Oligoastrocytoma: December 19, 2014 after 21 Cycles of Bevacizumab

Figure 7: Recurrent Right Frontoparietal Grade III Oligoastrocytoma: July 2015 after 30 Cycles of Bevacizumab

Issues with long-term survivors:
 We identified six long-term survivors (> 4 years), five males and one female.
 Average age: 38.83 years (range 21-51).
 Surgical details of the six patients:
 Total resection: 2 patients
 Substantial resection: 3 patients
 Partial resection: 1 patient
 Initial treatment with Stupp protocol
 Five cases were de novo gliomas, and one was a secondary glioma. Two recurred after the Stupp protocol and are currently on bevacizumab.
 Average survival is 79 months (range 48-108 months).

Figure 8: Recurrent Right Frontoparietal Grade III Oligoastrocytoma: April 2016 after 40 Cycles of Bevacizumab

Conclusion

Young age, good general condition, and the quality of surgical resection are predictive factors for a good

prognosis [5]. Molecular characterization in this group of patients is crucial to identify those at high risk of recurrence. Bevacizumab remains the recommended drug for recurrent glioblastomas due to its good tolerance.

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